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STABILITY AND *IN-VIVO* EFFICACY OF BILE SALTS CONTAINING VESICLES (BILOSOMES) FOR ORAL DELIVERY OF VACCINES AND POORLY SOLUBLE ACTIVE DRUG MOLECULES

Srinivas Bhairy*¹, Subrahmanyam Pitchika², Sandeep Maurya³, Jagadevappa Patil⁴

¹Formulation Scientist, Department of Formulation Research and Development, Oncology Division, Alembic Pharmaceuticals Limited, MN Science and Technology Park, Genome Valley, Hyderabad - 500 078, Telangana, INDIA.

²Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, Vagdevi College of Pharmacy and Research Centre, Brahmadevam, District Nellore – 524 346, Andhra Pradesh, INDIA.

³Research Scholar, Northern College, Haileybury Campus, 640 Latchford Street, Box 2060, Haileybury - POJ 1K0, Ontario, CANADA.

⁴Principal & Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, VT's S. S. Jondhle college of Pharmacy, Shahapur, District Thane-421 601, Maharashtra, INDIA.

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ABSTRACT

Vaccines delivered to the mucosal tissues can mimic natural infections and protect the first site of infection. Thus, oral delivery is becoming the most preferred mode of vaccination. Vesicular carrier systems (liposomes & niosomes) are one of the potential candidates for vaccine delivery by the oral route. However, oral vaccines have to overcome several barriers such as the extremely low pH of the stomach (instability in gastrointestinal (GIT) environment), the presence of proteolytic enzymes and bile salts as well as low permeability in the intestine makes it less applicable to be used for oral immunization. This necessitates larger and more frequent doses of antigens for vaccination. Modified drug delivery systems such as a lipid vesicle containing bile salts (bilosome), which prevents antigen degradation and enhances mucosal penetration are now under investigation of oral delivery of vaccines. This paper is briefly focused on new generation bilosomes, mechanism of working, stability aspects, and *in-vivo* efficacy. Based on the studies, it was observed that bilosomes exhibits best systems for oral immunization. Further to this, surface engineered bilosomes are more effective than bilosomes as such in various animal models and there is need of clinical trials to study the safety and efficacy of bilosomes. Similarly, more research to be done on scaling up factors for bilosomal systems to hit the commercial market.

Corresponding author

Srinivas Bhairy

Formulation Scientist,
Department of Formulation Research and Development,
Oncology Division, Alembic Pharmaceuticals Limited,
MN Science and Technology Park, Genome Valley,
Hyderabad - 500 078, Telangana, INDIA.

srbpharm4@gmail.com

+91-9503080706

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INTRODUCTION

Recently, the vesicular mode of delivery of drugs has gained attraction because of its improved therapeutic efficacy and stability. Vesicles are bilayered structures formed by hydration of lipid molecules and can be used for incorporating both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs. The drugs discovered over the years do not have very good effectiveness due to factors such as drug resistance, their inability to reach target sites, short residence time, poor bioavailability, lack of penetration, etc. So to overcome these challenges novel delivery systems are being investigated for effective delivery of these drugs. One such approach is vesicular delivery systems; these include liposomes, niosomes, ethosomes, transferosomes, pharmacosomes, sphingosomes, herbosomes, cubosomes, aquasomes, virosomes, enzymosomes, bilosomes, etc [1-4].

Mucosal sites are primary access points for most human pathogens; therefore, the induction of mucosal immunity plays an important role to prevent pathogen entry and to prevent infection. Oral vaccines offer significant benefits due to the ease of administration, better patient compliance, and non-invasive, needle-free administration. However, this route is marred by the harsh gastrointestinal environment which is detrimental to many vaccine formats as conventional vesicles (liposomes and niosomes) can cause dissolution and undergo enzymatic degradation in the gastrointestinal tract. In addition, the residence time of vaccines at the immune induction sites within the GIT (peyer's patches) is short due to GI transit. The target site for mucosal vaccine delivery systems is the M cells located within peyer's patches which are randomly distributed across the mucosa of the GIT, mainly in the jejunum. Due to the short exposure time of the vaccine to the peyer's patches, higher doses, or an increase in dosing frequency are often required to supply sufficient antigen delivery to elicit an immune response. However, this strategy of increasing dosing could potentially lead to reduced secretion of antigen-specific IgA levels, due to increased systemic tolerance to the vaccine. To address this, a range of delivery systems have been considered including bilosomes; these are bilayer vesicles constructed from non-ionic surfactants combined with the inclusion of bile salts which can stabilize the vesicles in the gastrointestinal tract by preventing membrane destabilization (figure 01). Liposomes and niosomes show poor activity on oral administration due to their instability in the GIT. Bile salts cause dissolution and enzymatic breakdown. The inclusion of bile salts in the membrane of these vesicles confers stability to the vesicles against bile acids. Vesicles in which bile salts are included are termed as bilosomes. Currently, non-ionic surfactant vesicle carrier systems, such as niosomes or bilosomes, are being employed to encapsulate/ associate vaccine antigens and administer via the oral route. The addition of bile salts (to form bilosomes) has been proposed to enhance antigen delivery by offering increased protection and retention of the antigen within the bilosomes when subjected to intestinal media containing bile acids, thus preventing premature release of antigen prior to reaching the target sites. Bile salts along with lipid content increase the bioavailability of enclosed bioactive substances and act as penetration enhancers. Bilosomes have been found to increase the bioavailability of drugs as they can readily be absorbed through the small intestine to the portal circulation (hepatic circulation). Through this circulation they approach the liver and release the drug, so also found to be an effective tool in drug targeting to the liver [5-11].

Figure 1: Graphical representation of Bilosomal system.

KEY BENEFITS

Bilosomes allow small quantities of antigens to be effective and also increase the efficacy of antigens which are weak when injected. Bilosomes do not require the use of live pathogens, making them a safe and effective alternative to traditional vaccines. This non-invasive system offers advantages in terms of user acceptance and compliance. The conventional injection method suffers from high relative costs and requires trained persons to administer the treatment. Less toxicity envelope is suitable for a wide range of therapeutic agents. The immune response could be manipulated through control of the size of the carrying vesicle. Bilosomes removes the cold-chain requirement for preparations such as a vaccine. Bilosomes provides a new delivery system improving patient compliance, its ease of administration and potentially providing extended patent life. The bilosomes patent represents a major step forward in vaccine technology by avoiding common problems associated with injections and increasing the efficacy of vaccines. The low toxicity envelope is suitable for a wide range of therapeutic agents [12-13].

MECHANISMS OF DRUG ABSORPTION ENHANCEMENT MEDIATED BY BILE ACIDS

As previously mentioned, bile acids are one of the most widely investigated classes of absorption enhancers. The influence of bile salts on drug absorption appears to be complex and it depends on the physicochemical properties of the drug and the interaction of the micelle with the physiological environment. It has been demonstrated that bile salts enhance the epithelial transport of hydrophilic drugs through the paracellular route and that of hydrophobic compounds through both paracellular and transcellular routes. The possible mechanism of the promotory effect on the action of hydrophilic drugs could be the incorporation of bile acids into the cell membrane where, at a certain concentration, they could form reverse micelles that included water molecules, thus creating hydrophilic pores in the cell membrane. Additionally, bile salts may increase the penetration of drugs via the paracellular route by binding calcium ions, thereby causing tight junctions between the cells to open, and by exerting a mucolytic effect. The underlying mechanisms for improvement of transcellular absorption include increasing the solubility and dissolution rate of otherwise slightly soluble drugs by micelle formation. Solubilization of lipophilic drugs within bile salt mixed micelles may facilitate diffusion through the aqueous diffusion layer, improving absorption. Micelles increase the permeability of the mucosal membrane by overcoming resistance at the aqueous diffusion layer. Solubilization by bile acids reduces particulate size and hence may allow the drug to enter the cell. However, drug solubilization may decrease the intermicellar free fraction of drugs, thus leading to a reduction in the absorption rate. Therefore, divergent results for drug absorption after co-administration with bile salts are presented in the literature. A suggested mechanism for the ability of bile salts to change the permeability of various cell membranes to drugs includes the interaction of bile salt micelles with membrane lipids, particularly phospholipid. It has been demonstrated that some bile salts inhibit the active efflux of P-glycoprotein (Pgp) substrates, probably indirectly by changing the lipid environment of the Pgp transporter or by interaction with Pgp itself.

STABILITY ASPECTS OF BILOSOMES

The main problems associated with storage of vesicles are aggregation, fusion and leakage of drug. Stability studies (whether in-process, in simulated fluids or during storage) are of vital prominence for successful development of pharmaceutical carrier systems. Decomposition of entrapped therapeutic agents may lead to decrease in their potency, whereas in the case of immunological preparations, denaturation of antigens may cause inadequate immune response making the subject prone to diseases.

In-process stability

Bilosomes containing diphtheria toxoid (DTx) were prepared by thin-film hydration. In-process stability and integrity of the entrapped antigen were assessed by sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE). The gel was run with the wells containing standard markers, native DTx and DTx loaded in nano-bilosomes. Clearly visible bands for pure as well as extracted antigen from the nano-bilosomes were observed for DTx in between 45 and 66 kDa. This shows integrity and in-process stability [14]. Bovine serum albumin (BSA) glucomannan (GM) bilosome vesicle size of 157 ± 3 nm, poly dispersity index of 0.287 ± 0.045 , the zeta potential of -21.8 ± 2.01 mV were freeze-dried and entrapped BSA in freeze-dried formulations was found to retain its structural and conformational stability as evident by SDS-PAGE and circular dichromism (CD) analysis. The same level of bands for standard BSA and BSA extracted from bilosomes and GM-bilosomes confirmed the chemical stability of BSA throughout the process. Moreover, no additional bands were observed in any of the samples suggesting no chemical degradation of BSA during its encapsulation in vesicular formulations [15]. Glucomannan-modified bilosomes containing tetanus toxoid (TT) and further stabilized by the freeze-drying method using lactose. The chemical integrity of entrapped TT into freeze-dried formulations was examined using SDS-PAGE. Chemical stability of the TT was maintained in all the vesicular formulations as evident by the symmetrical position of bands. Moreover, the absence of additional bands in all the samples further confirmed the chemical stability of TT throughout the process [16]. Liposomes with sodium glycocholate entrapped peptide (hhINS) were prepared by a reversed-phase evaporation method followed by homogenization. Far-ultraviolet CD spectroscopy is usually used to study the conformational stability of the rhINS. Preparative variables, such as homogenization pressure and the number of cycles, hydration time, amount of soybean phosphatidylcholine and insulin, and volume of organic solvents volume, at their extreme levels, and rhINS in sodium glycocholate liposomes prepared under extreme conditions, including the maximum amount of sodium glycocholate (soybean phosphatidylcholine: sodiumglycocholate ratio of 2: 1), the maximum amount of rhINS (rhINS: soybean phosphatidylcholine ratio of 0.0025: 1), maximum ether volume (water: ether ratio of 1: 7), the strongest ionic strength (1.2), and the extreme preparation conditions (hydration for 90 minutes; homogenization at 500 bar for six cycles), as well as a combination of the extreme conditions. No significant difference was observed as compared with free rhINS solution (the positive control), where a 53.1 ± 12.6 % reduction of the initial blood glucose level was obtained. Therefore, it was concluded that the bioactivity of insulin was well preserved after drug loading, confirming the results of the conformational study. The optimal formulation, which was prepared at less stress, showed good conformational stability and well-preserved bioactivity, with a hypoglycemic percentage of 45.2 ± 6.5 %, which is similar to that of the free rhINS solution [17].

Storage stability

Storage Stability studies are essential to explore the leaching of the entrapped agent from the vesicles during storage. The developed DTx loaded nanobilosomes showed more than 94 % antigen remained intact when stored at 2 ± 5 °C and 25 ± 2 °C at 70 % relative humidity (RH) for 30 days. An increase in particle size was observed when the temperature raised to 28 ± 1 °C [14]. The bioactive triterpenoid saponin components of ginseng fruit were loaded into a combination of proliposome with sodium deoxycholate were stable at 4 ± 2 °C and 37 °C for 90 days when they are evaluated for physical appearance, vesicle size, and encapsulation efficiency [18]. The mannosylated bilosomes of *Leishmania dono vani* antigen were showed stability for 3 months when they are stored at 4 ± 1 °C, 25 ± 2 °C/ 60 ± 5 % RH. The increase of particle size after 3 months was observed from $0.208.5$ μm to $0.357.7$ μm possibly due to aggregation of vesicles and degradation of phospholipids at a higher temperature (25 ± 2 °C/ 60 ± 5 % RH) [19].

Stability in simulated biological milieu: simulated gastric fluid (SGF), simulated intestinal fluid (SIF) and bile salt solutions

It is crucial to interpret the stability of vesicular carriers and encapsulated peptides and proteins when confronted by gastric pH, bile salts and GI enzymes as the intact fraction of the vesicles predominantly influences the associated *in-vivo* response. However, it is somehow challenging, to perceive the fate of the vesicles in the GI tract by sampling or imaging tools.

Bilosomal systems were incubated in SGF pH 1.2, SIF pH 6.8 and phosphate buffer solution (PBS) (pH 7.4) having two different concentrations (5 and 20 mM) of bile salt (sodium deoxycholate, Na-DOC) to simulate the effect of bile salts by evaluating particle size and % BSA retained. Bilosomes and GM-bilosomes of BSA were found stable as no significant change in quality attributes was observed upon incubation in presence of Na-DOC solution (5 and 20 mM). There is only a $\pm 5\mu\text{m}$ change in particle size and $\pm 10\%$ changes in % BSA retained was observed [15]. A similar study was carried for TT surface engineered bilosomes. GM-bilosomes were found quite stable as evident by vesicle size and significantly a higher percentage of TT retained in comparison with niosomes and bilosomes. Incubation in presence of Na-DOC solution (5 and 20 mM) resulted in a significant loss of entrapped TT in the case of niosomes as compared to bilosomes and GM-bilosomes [16]. The protective effect on rhINS-loaded sodium glycocholate liposomes was studied using SGF, SIF, and or α -chymotrypsin solution (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, in PBS, pH 7.8). In presence of pepsin, rhINS content in the conventional cholesterol liposomes was remarkably decreased from 100 % to less than 5 % of the initial value. After 4 hours liposomes containing bile salts all showed some resistance to pepsin because less degradation of rhINS was observed. Sodium glycocholate provided the best protection of liposomal rhINS, preserving 50 % of rhINS at 4 hours. This may be attributable to the enzyme-inhibiting ability of sodium glycocholate. However, surprisingly, as the amount of sodium glycocholate increased further, less protection of liposomal rhINS was observed. As the sodium glycocholate: soybean phosphatidylcholine ratio in the liposome formulation increased from 1: 8 to 1: 2, the amount of intact insulin decreased from 70 % to 28 % at 4 hours. This can be explained by the increased flexibility of the lipid bilayers due to the presence of excessive amounts of sodium glycocholate, which may lead to the leakage of rhINS [17]. Another study showed that when bilosomal formulations (5: 4: 1 Monopalmitoyl glycerol (MPG): cholesterol (Chol) : Diacetyl phosphate (DCP) with 100 mM bile salt) are exposed to SGF and SIF. In SGF, bilosome vesicle size increases from 6.44 ± 0.05 μm to 11.9 ± 0.57 μm after exposure for 15 minutes but did not significantly increase in size thereafter. The drop in pH resulted in a reduction in zeta potential from -125 mV to -47 mV and no antigen lost from the formulation was observed. However, when bilosomal formulation transferred to SIF, the bilosomes decreased back to their original size, and moved to a more negative, but not fully restored, zeta potential and antigen loading was decreased from 32 % to 7.8 - 8.5 % [20]. The stability of recombinant hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) bilosomal formulation was studied in SGF (pH 1.2), SIF (pH 7.5), and different concentrations of bile salt (5 and 20 mM). It was observed that 90 % and 95 % of HBsAg was retained in SGF and SIF respectively. Similarly, 95 % and 85 % of HBsAg was retained in vesicles at 5mM and 20mM concentration [21]. The mannosylated bilosomes of soluble *Leishmania dono vani* antigen and BSA formulations were evaluated for stability in SGF and SIF, there was no significant change in vesicle size and performance was observed [19]. The non-ionic surfactant vesicles prepared by the addition of sodium salt of deoxycholic acid using BSA as model antigen and was evaluated for bile salt solution of 5 mM and 20 mM deoxycholate in carbonate. It was observed that there was no significant loss of retained antigen in 5 mM solution and only 85 % was retained in 20 mM solution [5]. Stability of recombinant HBsAg (MW 24 kDa) bilosomes and mannosylated bilosomes were studied in SGF and SIF. Both formulations, were significantly highly stable in the GIT fluids when compared to conventional niosomes as number of vesicles remaining in niosomes were found to be lesser after 2 hours. Similarly, a significant decrease in percent residual antigen content in the case of niosomes was observed when compared to bilosomes and mannosylated bilosomes. This reduction in vesicle count, as well as loss in antigen content, maybe due to the inherent instability of the outer lipid membrane of the niosomes at acidic pH and in the presence of bile salts whereas bilosomes remain stable with an intact lipid membrane, therefore retain a significant amount of entrapped antigens. Moreover, mannosylated bilosomes are more stable than uncoated bilosomes [3]. The integrity of insulin loaded sodium glycolate (SGC) bilosomes and conventional liposomes were studied in SGF and *ex-vivo* GI media from rats. SGC-Lip and cholesterol (CH)-Lip showed similar size (around 200 nm) and size distribution, the entrapment efficiency of insulin was 30.23 ± 0.84 % and 28.11 ± 0.93 %, respectively. SGC-Lip possessed lower zeta potential in comparison with CH-Lip due to liposomal membrane insertion of negatively charged glycocholate. Free insulin was rapidly degraded in SGF, fasted state (FaS) SGF, SIF, and fed state (FeS) SIF. No insulin signal could be detected by High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) at 15 minutes, indicating complete degradation at this time point. SGC-Lip reserved 48.5 ± 2.6 % of the initial encapsulated insulin in SGF while it was 33.0 ± 1.6 % for CH-Lip in SGF. In presence of gastric media, after 4 hours incubation with intestinal fluid, SGC-Lip reserved 20.5 ± 1.8 % of the initial encapsulated insulin. However, only 9.2 ± 1.8 % of the initially entrapped insulin was retained in CH-Lip. Since the concentration of the bile salts and enzyme *in-vivo* is higher than 1: 1 dilution with GI enzyme fluids used and both SGC-Lip and CH-Lip would degrade more quickly during transit through the GI tract [22].

The stability of the HBsAg-loaded cholera toxin B (CTB)-conjugated bilosomal system was evaluated for % antigen entrapment, size, and shape in SGF (USP, pH 1.2), SIF (USP, pH 7.5), and in bile salt solutions. The stability studies on the formulation indicate that about 86 % and 91 % of HBsAg were retained in the vesicles in SGF (USP, pH 1.2) and SIF (USP, pH 7.5), respectively. Assessment of stability carried out in the bile salt solutions showed that about 91 % and 80 % of HBsAg was retained in the vesicles at 5 and 20 mM concentrations of bile salt, respectively [23]. The stability of Bilosomes with antigen BSA was conjugated with CTB was evaluated in SGF (pH1.2), SIF (pH7.5), and different concentrations of bile salts. Results suggest that bilosomes are comparably more stable in simulated fluids than niosomes, however, the difference was insignificant. It has been reported that bile salt concentration in healthy humans has been in a range between 5 and 20 mM. Therefore, the stability of formulations was also tested in these two extreme concentrations. It was observed that at 5 mM concentrations around 92 – 95 % of BSA was retained in vesicles, whereas at higher bile salt concentration only bilosomes retained 84 % of BSA compared to niosomes (~52 %). It can be inferred from results that bilosomes exhibit relatively better stability compared to niosomes. The intactness of surface anchored CTB was also checked by agglutination assay, where a negligible reduction in the biological activity of CTB was noticed after treatment with SGF (pH 1.2), SIF (pH 7.5), and bile salt solutions (5 and 20 mM) [24].

IN-VIVO EFFICACY OF BILOSOMES

Bilosomes of recombinant H3N2 sub-unit protein vesicles are spherical and the vesicles meet the criteria of being within the optimum size range and charge for increased uptake within the target site of the peyer's patches. The necessity of the addition of bile salts to enhance protection and delivery is circumvented as both antigen retention and antigen delivery to the target site after oral administration was comparable. The lipid content within the drug delivery system was able to trigger sufficient lymphatic transport of halofantrine thus, increasing bioavailability. No significant differences in percentage antigen or vesicle recovery between different dose concentrations in the organs collected after a 30 minutes time point and overall percentage recovery of antigen are comparable (40–70 %) between all doses administered based on the initial dose [25]. The serum anti-HBsAg titre obtained after oral administration of B3 (high dose, 50 µg/dose) was comparable with titres obtained after intramuscular administration of alum adsorbed HBsAg (10 µg, control group) but the responses obtained following oral administration of B3 (high dose, 50 µg/dose) were significant when compared with B1 (low dose, 10 µg/dose). All the orally administered formulations produced significant sIgA responses in mucosal secretions when compared with alum adsorbed HBsAg (control group), which was administered intramuscularly. Fluorescence microscopy demonstrated effective and efficient uptake of bilosomes by the gut-associated lymphoid tissue (GALT) and therefore it can be concluded that bilosomes are efficient in transporting vaccines to the peyer's patches, resulting in both mucosal and systemic immune responses [21]. *Leishmania* antigen was loaded in mannosylated bilosomes and the sustained release of antigen from formulation confirmed by the korsmeyer-peppas kinetic model. The mechanism of release was erosion and swelling leading to diffusion for antigen release from mannosylated bilosomes. Peyer's patches of mice to which dye was administered, showed that the dye was unable to target the cells as the fluorescence occurs outside the cells but when the dye was administered to *leishmania* loaded mannosylated bilosomal formulation, it showed accumulation in the cells which were confirmed by fluorescence inside the cells due to coumarin 6 in the formulation. It showed that mannosylated bilosomes can be used for targeting the antigen to M cells. Thus, the mannosylated bilosomes facilitate the oral delivery of antigen to the macrophages of the liver, spleen through M cells, and could be able to produce immunization against visceral *leishmaniasis* [19].

The preparation of A. Texas (Surface antigen from inactivated influenza virus, strain A. Texas: H3N2) in bilosomes resulted in the generation of high titres of influenza virus-specific IgG, IgG1, and IgG2a which were significantly greater than those achieved with A. Texas administered in carbonate buffer alone. Furthermore, oral delivery of A. Texas entrapped in bilosomes resulted in immune responses comparable with those achieved with the conventional subcutaneous injection of A. Texas. Entrapment of the A. Texas in bilosomes was essential to achieve elevated antibody responses, as merely mixing the A. Texas with bilosomes did not result in significantly increased antibody production. This suggests that either entrapment of A. Texas in bilosomes is required to protect the antigen from degradation in the gut or physical association between the bilosome vesicle and the antigen is required for an adjuvant effect, as has been shown for parenterally administered liposomes and non-ionic surfactant vesicles [5]. The serum anti-HBsAg titre obtained after oral administration of mannosylated bilosomes with 50 µg/dose was comparable with titres obtained after intramuscular administration of alum adsorbed HBsAg (10 µg, control group), which is significantly higher than all other treated groups. sIgA levels in salivary, vaginal, intestinal, and nasal secretions of BALB/c mice after 42 days of immunization using various formulations were evaluated. Negligible sIgA response (statistically insignificant) was observed with intramuscularly administered alum-adsorbed HBsAg. This may be credited to the fact that parenterally administered antigen cannot stimulate the mucosal immune system. While orally administered bilosomal formulations produced significant higher sIgA responses in mucosal secretions. The mucosal immune response was measured as IgA titers. Mannosylated bilosomes showed higher cell-mediated immunity than plain uncoated bilosomes [3]. The bioavailability of Cyclosporin A-pro-bilosomes is as high as about 1.23 times that of Neoral® capsules, highlighting the enhancing effect of bile salt on absorption. Also, the effect of Cyclosporin A-pro-gelatin bilosomes on oral absorption is better than CyclosporinA-pro-gelatin bilosomes, with a relative oral bioavailability of 1.27 times. This might be due to the gelatin core of gelatin bilosomes, which protects the structure of bilosomes from GI fluid damage. It is speculated that enhanced uptake of bilosomes as integral vesicles through the M-cells in the peyer's patches and increased transportation through the lymphatic path-way might be the principle mechanisms. The results confirm that there is a certain amount of drug found in lymph, but in very limited proportion. It is known that lipid-based vehicles including self-emulsifying drug delivery systems can enhance oral absorption of the drug via the lymphatic system. However, the cumulative lymphatic absorption of Neoral® is just as low as 1%. It seems that the M cell pathway should not be the mechanism governing facilitated oral delivery by bilosomes [26].

Oral bioavailability was measured in rats by administering the ginseng fruit saponins (GFS), GFS Tablets, and proliposomes of GFS orally. The pharmacokinetic parameters of GFS, zhenyuan tablets and P-GFS in rats were respectively listed as follows: T_{max} 0.25 hours, C_{max} 474.96 ± 66.06 ng/ml and $AUC_{0 \rightarrow \infty}$ 733.32 ± 113.82 ng/ml hours for GFS; T_{max} 0.31 ± 0.043 hours, C_{max} 533.94 ± 106.54 ng/ml and $AUC_{0 \rightarrow \infty}$ 1151.38 ± 198.29 ng/ml hours for zhenyuan tablets; T_{max} 0.5 hours, C_{max} 680.62 ± 138.051 ng/ml and $AUC_{0 \rightarrow \infty}$ 2082.49 ± 408.33 ng/ml hours for the proliposomes GFS. The bioavailability of proliposomes GFS was nearly 284 % and 181 % of the GFS and zhengyuan tablets respectively. The values of C_{max} , T_{max} , $T_{1/2}$, $AUC_{0 \rightarrow \infty}$, and Cl_{F_obs} (ml/ hours) for ginsenoside Re in proliposomes showed obvious differences. The higher values of C_{max} and $AUC_{0 \rightarrow \infty}$ of ginsenoside Re in proliposomes compared with control and zhenyuan tablets suggested that liposomes containing bile salt formulation could improve the bioavailability of ginsenoside Re. The possible reasons for this are that liposomes containing sodium deoxycholate by facilitating the transition from liposomes to mixed micelles could increase the stability and the permeability of ginsenoside Re in the intestinal tract and protect the ginsenoside Re degradation from the enzyme. Also, the endocytosis by epithelial cells and the intestinal lymphatic transport reduce the first-pass metabolism. A further pharmacokinetic study suggested that proliposomes increased the oral availability of GFS. The controlled release and protection from the enzyme degradation of ginsenoside Re and sodium deoxycholate may significantly decrease the elimination of GFS and enhance absorption in the gastrointestinal tract. Moreover, the proliposomes GFS had good stability at room temperature [18]. A study was conducted to evaluate the oral bioavailability of diphtheria toxoid using nanobilosomes. The serum anti-DTx IgG titres obtained after oral administration of DTxNB3 (high dose, 2 Lf per dose) were comparable with that obtained after intramuscular administration of alum-adsorbed DTx (0.5 Lf, control group). All the nanobilosomal formulations, administered orally, produced significant sIgA responses in mucosal secretions similarly the alum-adsorbed DTx (control group), administered intramuscular alum-adsorbed formulations and untrapped DTx, 2 Lf did not elicit detectable sIgA in the mucosal secretions. However, the four times higher untrapped DTx was unable to produce any significant immune response, both at systemic as well as mucosal levels. This can ostensibly be attributed due to the lack of protection of the antigen, leading eventually to its denaturation and destruction by the acidic gastric environment as well as by other intestinal enzymes [14]. The TT containing surface engineered bilosomes were evaluated for their oral bioavailability. GM-bilosomes exhibited significantly higher uptake in comparison with bilosomes and niosomes while this difference was insignificant between niosomes and bilosomes. GM-bilosomes exhibited 2.50 folds and 2.17 folds higher uptake in comparison with niosomes and bilosomes, respectively. At the end of the day 35, orally administered free TT elicited the lowest IgG titre among all the formulations. A significantly higher IgG titre was observed in the case of niosomes as compared to orally administered free TT. Bilosomes further elicited significantly higher titre in comparison with niosomes and orally administered free TT. In line, GM-bilosomes further improved the IgG titre which was significantly higher in comparison with oral TT, niosomes, and bilosomes [16].

The recombinant baculovirus (Bac) associated bilosomes were evaluated against HEV71 infection in mice for its oral bioavailability. The mice immunized with Bac-VP1 significantly induced higher mucosal IgA levels than the mice immunized with inactive Bac-VP1. Again, the live Bac-VP1 associated with bilosomes showed higher mucosal responses compared with inactive Bac-VP1 associated with bilosomes. The mucosal responses elicited by mice immunized with bilosomes associated with Bac-VP1 were also significantly higher than those of mice immunized with non-associated Bac-VP1. The mice immunized subcutaneously with live Bac-VP1 significantly induced higher VP1 specific antibody response compared with mice orally immunized with either live Bac-VP1 alone or associated with bilosomes. Nevertheless, mice orally vaccinated with Bac-VP1 associated with bilosomes were able to induce stronger immune responses compared to live Bac-VP1 or inactive Bac-VP1 associated with bilosomes as indicated by the high levels of VP1-specific IgG and mucosal IgA antibodies in enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay [27]. Oral treatment with 'empty' bilosomes, oral untrapped TT (50 μ g/mouse), and bilosome entrapped TT at the lower dose (TT 40 μ g/mouse). Both subcutaneous injection with TT (50 μ g/mouse) and bilosome entrapped TT at the higher dose (TT 200 μ g/mouse) resulted in the production of significant specific IgG1 antibody titres by week 3 post-treatment. The study demonstrates that tetanus toxoid entrapped in bilosomes is capable of inducing a T helper type 2 response characterized by systemic IgG1. There was a clear dose-dependency, with specific TT IgG1 antibody titres only being induced with a higher dose of TT (200 μ g/dose) and not the lower concentration of 40 μ g/dose. This is not surprising since it has been established that oral delivery normally requires a much higher concentration of protein and multiple doses compared with parenteral administration to achieve the same level of efficacy [28]. Hypoglycemic activity and oral bioavailability of insulin-loaded liposomes containing bile salts were evaluated in rats. The highest oral bioavailability of approximately 8.5 % and 11 % could be achieved for SGC-liposomes in non-diabetic and diabetic rats respectively, which was among the highest insulin bioavailability values ever obtained by the oral route. The most significant blood glucose reduction resulted from insulin-loaded SGC-liposomes, which produced maximum blood glucose reduction of 63 % at 10 hours after oral administration and returned to normal at around 20 hours. SGC was found to provide the best protection of encapsulated rhINS against pepsin, trypsin, and α -chymotrypsin. However, liposomes with 80 nm particle size showed smaller oral bioavailability than liposomes with a bigger particle size of 150 nm and 400 nm, which was especially significant in diabetic rats. It was found that the particles should be controlled within a certain size range to be taken up efficiently by the M-cell uptake pathway. Neither particles with much smaller size nor those with a much bigger size could be absorbed efficiently. As observed in this study, liposomes of 2 μ m were too big to be taken up by the M-cells, while liposomes of 80 nm were too small to elicit efficient internalization and absorption. Another finding regarding the effect of particle size is the quick peak time (C_{max} , C_{min}) of about 2.5 hours for 80 nm liposomes as compared to 8–10 hours for liposomes with larger sizes. There seem to be alternative absorption pathways (trans-epithelial) other than the M-cell pathway for smaller liposomes. The particles may be absorbed much earlier in the upper GIT [29]. The serum anti-HBsAg titre obtained following oral administration of CTB1 (20 μ g dose) was comparable with that of the titres of intramuscular administration of 10 μ g of alum-adsorbed HBsAg, control group. However, the responses obtained following oral administration of CTB1 (20 μ g dose) were statistically significantly different, when compared with orally administered CTB2 (10 μ g dose) and untrapped HBsAg (10 μ g).

Orally administered CTB-conjugated bilosomal formulations (CTB1 and CTB2) produced significantly higher sIgA responses in mucosal secretions vis-à-vis the intramuscular injection of 10 µg alum-adsorbed HBsAg, control group. The intramuscular administered alum-adsorbed HBsAg and orally administered untrapped HBsAg could not even bring about measurable sIgA in the mucosal secretions [23]. Oral immunization with bilosomes conjugated with CTB significantly increased IgG levels compared with CTB without bilosomal formulations. It has been observed that BSA emulsified with Freund's complete adjuvant also produced almost equivalent IgG titre when administered subcutaneously. At the other extreme, when three doses of BSA were orally administered to produce a primary immune response, almost all formulations exhibited an increase in IgG response except CTB-conjugated bilosomes. Probably this may be due to saturation of IgG levels achieved through the oral route [24]. To investigate the efficacy of the bilosomes containing the recombinant HA (rHA) directed against influenza viruses were administered to ferrets orally on days 0, 3, 14, and 17, and 14 days later challenged with a clinical rHA isolate of influenza. The bilosome vaccine incorporating the rHA shows a reduced median temperature differential change compared to a dose of empty bilosomes suggesting that the antigen containing bilosomes via the oral route provided strong protection from fever. After analysing nasal washes for inflammatory cells, the bilosome plus rHA vaccine also promoted a reduction in viral cell load counts compared to bilosomes administered without antigen. Thus, the bilosome formulation containing the influenza vaccine promoted protection against fever and suppressed lung inflammation to extents comparable to empty vesicles showing promising results for vaccine delivery via the oral route [20].

CONCLUSION

Vesicular drug delivery systems are emerging with the diverse application in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and cosmeceuticals, and food industries. The delivery of the drug directly to the site of infection and it's leading to a reduction of drug toxicity with no adverse effects. It also reduces the cost of therapy by imparting better biopharmaceutical properties to the drug, resulting in improved bioavailability and especially in case of poorly soluble drugs. Oral administration remains the favoured method of drug delivery by patients and drugs to be successfully absorbed by the body. It requires the active molecule to transit through the stomach and then to be transferred across the intestinal wall to the bloodstream. For a majority of vaccines and biologic therapeutics, this is not an option due to a 1 % uptake of the dose given. Approximately 1/3 of small molecule drugs also face oral absorption challenges. Lipid-based carrier platforms have been recently investigated for oral vaccination, it has been pointed out that these lipid-based vehicles (such as liposomes) are susceptible to bile salts and enzymatic degradation in the GI tract. Therefore, a relatively stable (in the GI tract) lipid-based carrier is required for future oral drug/vaccination delivery. A colloidal delivery system consisting of bilosomes, similar to niosomes (nonionic surfactant base vesicles), but with have incorporated bile salts into the vesicular lipid bilayer membrane. Bilosomes are made of naturally occurring lipids, which makes them highly biocompatible. The bilosomes components have also been shown to possess inherent adjuvant properties when associated with antigen. Bilosome based vaccine produced both systemic as well as a mucosal immune response which was equivalent to the immune response produced by the subcutaneous route. As discussed, the bilosomes have great potential as oral vaccine delivery. However, the method of preparation and sterilization of bilosomal preparations remains an issue. While aseptic manufacturing and filtration are the most commonly utilized methods of producing parenteral liposomes, the procedures involved are time-consuming and the equipment is extremely expensive and difficult to maintain. This impedes the scaling-up of liposomal formulations manufacturing and ascribes a high cost to such preparations. Hence, there remains a need for the development of a widely applicable preparation method a sterilization technique, one that is efficient, cost-effective, and can maintain the physicochemical stability and encapsulated content of the preparation.

ABBREVIATIONS

GIT	- Gastrointestinal tract
Pgp	- P-glycoprotein
DTx	- Diphtheria toxoid
SDS-PAGE	- Sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis
BSA	- Bovine serum albumin
CD	- Circular dichromism
GM	- Glucomannan
TT	- Tetanus toxoid
RH	- Relative humidity
SGF	- Simulated gastric fluid
SIF	- Simulated intestinal fluid
PBS	- Phosphate buffer solution
Na-DOC	- Sodium deoxycholate
MPG	- Monopalmitoyl glycerol
Chol	- Cholesterol
DCP	- Diacetyl phosphate
HBsAg	- Recombinant hepatitis B surface antigen
SGC	- Sodium glycholate
FaS	- Fasted state
FeS	- Fed state
HPLC	- High performance liquid chromatography
CTB	- Cholera toxin B
GALT	- Gut-associated lymphoid tissue
GFS	- Ginseng fruit saponins
Bac	- Baculovirus

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflict of interest

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